

Supplementary Material

1 CATEGORY SYSTEM

Table S1: Complete category system derived from results from the qualitative focus group study.

Category	Subcategory 1	Subcategory 2
Perceived motivators regarding CCU adoption	Sustainability Reusing climate damaging CO ₂ Permanently binding CO ₂ Reduction of climate damaging CO ₂ Relief for the environment Saving fossil resources Reduced emissions compared to conventional production processes Cost savings through fewer manufacturing steps and shortened supply chain	
Perceived barriers regarding CCU adoption	Health Economic factors Environmental aspects	Risks due to prolonged use Risks due to direct contact to skin Concerns regarding quality Expected higher prices Artificial adherence to CO ₂ sources Re-emission of CO ₂ Supplanting other solutions Uncertainty regarding impact
User requirements regarding CCU products	Health compatibility Quality Information materials Communication efforts	Compliance with quality standards Quality assessment by authority Interaction with other technologies Impact certification Detailed information regarding advantages and disadvantages Tailored to target group Avoiding negative associations

2 OVERVIEW OF ITEMS INCLUDED IN STATISTICAL ANALYSES

Table S2: Descriptive statistics of the items included in the analyses, including the construct names, abbreviations, as well as the Cronbach's alpha for the separately computed variables based on the item. The table also includes the references for the sources that were used as the starting point for the item formulation, before discussion, reformulation and refinement.

abbr.	item	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	references
	Environmental behaviour ($\alpha = .83$) The following statements relate to your behaviour. For each statement, please indicate the extent to which it applies to you personally.			adapted from Kannapin (2000)
eb1	I'd rather put on a warm sweater than heat up the entire room.	4.58	1.21	
eb2	I am careful not to take unnecessarily long and hot showers to keep my hot water consumption low.	4.32	1.34	
eb3	I ensure low energy consumption when buying household appliances.	4.70	1.14	
eb4	I always travel longer distances by train.	3.06	1.59	
eb5	As a matter of principle, I do not travel by plane.	3.39	1.67	
eb6	I try to avoid waste through unnecessary packaging, unnecessary plastic bags, etc.	4.44	1.27	
eb7	I specifically buy products that have a low impact on the environment in their production and use.	3.87	1.16	
eb8	When I buy textiles, I make sure that they do not contain harmful substances.	3.91	1.24	
	Readiness for innovation ($\alpha = .89$) The following statements address how you deal with technical innovations. Please indicate to what extent you agree with the statements.			adapted from Neyer et al. (2012)
inno1	I keep an eye out for new products regularly.	3.72	1.24	
inno2	I often look for information on new products that might interest me.	3.96	1.20	
inno3	I am usually the first in my circle of friends and acquaintances to try new products.	3.09	1.33	
inno4	I think it's interesting to try new products.	4.14	1.23	
	Motivators ($\alpha = .93$) Using CCU products and innovations can have different benefits. What do you think?			derived from qualitative results
mo1	Degradation of climate-damaging CO ₂	4.16	1.13	

abbr.	item	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	references
mo2	Reuse of climate-damaging CO ₂	4.10	1.19	
mo3	Conserving fossil fuels	4.30	1.16	
mo4	Reduction of CO ₂ -emissions compared to conventional production.	4.11	1.10	
mo5	Possibility to 'permanently' bind CO ₂ in long-term CCU products	4.13	1.07	
mo6	Sustainability through the reuse of CO ₂	4.20	1.11	
mo7	Relief for the environment	4.39	1.14	
mo8	Potential cost savings through shortened supply chain/ manufacturing steps	4.09	1.13	
	Barriers ($\alpha = .87$) Perceived disadvantages can also strongly influence the use of CCU products. What is your opinion on the following statements.			
ba1	I am against artificially adhering to CO ₂ sources.	2.99	1.14	
ba2	I question a final, climate-neutral disposal of CCU products.	3.69	1.10	
ba3	I fear manipulation of consumers by marketing measures.	4.01	1.20	
ba4	I fear too little environmental impact.	3.55	1.06	
ba5	I fear a high energy cost in the manufacturing of the CCU products.	3.92	1.04	
ba6	I fear a re-release of the CO ₂ when the products are disposed of.	3.77	1.16	
ba7	I fear only short-term sequestration of the CO ₂	3.67	1.02	
	Prior knowledge ($\alpha = .96$) How would you rate your knowledge of processes and structures regarding CO ₂ use?			self-generated
pk1	CO ₂ storage	4.16	2.60	
pk2	Use of CO ₂ as raw material (CCU)	3.77	2.48	
pk3	CO ₂ capture	3.99	2.60	
pk4	CO ₂ transport	3.98	2.55	
	General acceptance ($\alpha = .82$) We are interested in how you feel about the use of products based on CO ₂ . Please indicate to what extent you agree with the following statements.			adapted from Davis (1989)
ga1	I think CO ₂ -based products are acceptable.	3.88	1.10	
ga2	I think CO ₂ -based products are useful.	3.83	1.08	
ga3	I would use CO ₂ -based products.	3.86	1.10	
ga4	I support the use of CO ₂ -based products.	3.77	1.22	
ga5	For me, the use of CO ₂ -based products is	3.86	1.10	

abbr.	item	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	references
	reasonable.			
ga6	I am unsure regarding CO ₂ -based products' quality.	3.65	1.15	
ga7	I reject the use of CO ₂ -based products.	2.76	1.16	

REFERENCES

- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS quarterly* , 319–340
- Kannapin, O. (2000). *Prädiktormuster selbstberichteten Umweltverhaltens [Predictor patterns of self-reported environmental behaviour]*. Ph.D. thesis, Staats-und Universitätsbibliothek Hamburg Carl von Ossietzky
- Neyer, F. J., Felber, J., and Gebhardt, C. (2012). Entwicklung und validierung einer kurzskala zur erfassung von technikbereitschaft [development and validation of a brief measure of technology commitment]. *Diagnostica*